

Community knowledge, attitudes, and practices toward Toxoplasmosis and the epidemiological role of birds in its transmission in the district of Lahore, Punjab, Pakistan

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Abstract

Toxoplasmosis, a zoonotic disease caused by the protozoan parasite *Toxoplasma gondii*, poses significant public health and economic challenges by infecting humans, animals, and birds globally. Birds, as intermediate hosts, play a critical role in the transmission cycle of this parasite, highlighting the importance of community awareness regarding its epidemiological impacts. This study assessed the knowledge, attitudes, and practices (KAPs) related to toxoplasmosis among residents in Lahore, Punjab, Pakistan. Using close-ended questionnaires with 59 structured questions, responses from 200 randomly selected participants across five tehsils were analyzed. Findings revealed that although 45.5% of the respondents were aware of the existence of toxoplasmosis but 64% lacked knowledge about its transmission. Commonly identified transmission routes included consumption of raw or undercooked meat, contact with contaminated soil, untreated water, and raw vegetables. Additionally, 58% of participants supported disease control measures, though 59% were unaware of available treatments. These results underscore a moderate level of community awareness among the residents of Lahore and emphasize the need for targeted educational campaigns utilizing the One Health Approach to mitigate the risks associated with this parasitic disease. Community engagement and intersectoral collaboration are imperative to enhance public health outcomes and prevent the spread of toxoplasmosis.

Keywords: *Toxoplasma*, Zoonosis, One Health, Public health, Parasitic diseases

Introduction

Birds, being widely distributed and diurnally active across diverse habitats, are among the most observed vertebrates in nature, yet their survival is increasingly threatened by a range of health challenges (Aghayan et al., 2024). Parasitic infestation is one of the significant concerns due to its frequency and the adverse effects it can have on the populations of birds in heavily parasitized regions (Brito et al., 2017). These infestations can lead to severe infections and even fatalities within affected communities (Vogt, 2023). Parasitism in birds is well documented, with protozoa, nematodes, cestodes, and trematodes being the most common endoparasites (Allievi et al., 2024; Li et al., 2024).

Wild and domestic birds are not only vulnerable to a range of microorganisms that threaten their own health but also act as carriers of pathogens transmissible to mammals, including humans (Ebani et al., 2021). These avian species, diverse in their behaviors, feeding habits, and habitats, often carry pathogens in their intestinal tract, subsequently excreting them in surroundings and posing risk to other birds and mammals (Nabi et al., 2021). This risk is heightened in farm areas, where wild birds frequently interact with livestock, serving as vectors of diseases that can lead to significant economic losses (Benskin et al., 2009). Furthermore, the fecal matter of birds contaminates pastureland, water supplies, and feed, creating an avenue for the transmission of infectious and parasitic agents to domestic livestock, thus reinforcing their role in the spread of zoonotic diseases (Ebani & Mancianti, 2022).

Toxoplasmosis is a prevalent zoonotic disease caused by the intracellular protozoan parasite *Toxoplasma gondii* (*T. gondii*). Recognized as a significant public health concern, this infection affects both humans and animals, leading to substantial economic losses (Delgado et al., 2022). Globally, as estimated 1 to 2 billion individuals are infected with *T. gondii* (Smith et al. 2021), with at least one-third of the population demonstrating antibodies against this parasite (Flegr et al., 2020). Infection rates vary widely across regions, ranging from 10% and 80% (Zaki et al., 2024).

Domestic and wild felids are the only definitive hosts of *T. gondii*, which completes its sexual stage of life cycle within them and releases numerous oocysts in their feces, contaminating the environment (Dubey et al., 2020). Warm-blooded animals, including birds, can act as intermediate hosts by ingesting meat with tissue cysts or sporulated oocysts from contaminated surroundings (Pagmadulam, 2018; Montoya, 2004). Felines get *T. gondii* from eating infected rodents and birds. Birds, in turn, spread the infection to humans and other animals when they are eaten as food or used as protein source (Bata et al., 2021). Human food like water, fruits, and vegetables can also be contaminated with *T. gondii* feces. Eating these contaminated foods can cause toxoplasmosis in humans. Ingesting meat from infected birds is also a major cause of infection in humans (Almeria & Dubey, 2021). The consequences

of toxoplasmosis are especially severe in pregnant women, as the parasite can be transmitted to the fetus, potentially leading to profound neurological consequences (Bonetti et al., 2025).

Countries such as Pakistan (Tayyub et al. 2022; Khan et al. 2020; Naveed et al. 2019; Nazir et al. 2018), Iran (Abdoli et al. 2018), Canada (Reiling et al. 2019), Italy (Gazzonis et al. 2021; Mancianti et al. 2020; Nardoni et al. 2019; Gazzonis et al. 2018), Portugal (Lopes et al. 2021), Türkiye (Karakavuk et al. 2018), Spain (Darwich et al. 2012), and Nigeria (Bata et al. 2021) show varying prevalence rates of 3 to 90% of toxoplasmosis in wild birds.

Toxoplasmosis is prevalent among animals and humans in Pakistan, affecting approximately 33% of the human population with variations based on diet and climate (Shah et al., 2013). In Mardan 42.2% of goats and 44.1% of sheep tested positive for *T. gondii* (Shah et al. 2013), while 43.5% of cattle in Khanewal carried antibodies (Tasawar et al., 2013). Backyard poultry, a key protein source in rural areas, showed a 36.3% prevalence of antibodies in Faisalabad, Pakistan (Akhtar et al., 2014). Additionally, wild birds and rodents in Sahiwal, Faisalabad, Chiniot, Jhang and Okara, Punjab, Pakistan have been found to carry *T. gondii* antibodies, demonstrating the zoonotic potential of wildlife transmitting toxoplasmosis to humans living nearby (Ali et al., 2020; Rizwan et al., 2023).

The lack of awareness surrounding protozoan parasitic diseases, particularly toxoplasmosis, remains a significant factor contributing to its prevalence among animals and humans. Understanding knowledge, attitudes, and practices (KAPs) is crucial for implementing effective control and prevention strategies to mitigate the impacts of this disease. While extensive KAP studies have been conducted globally in countries like Indonesia (Nurseha et al. 2023), Ethiopia (Desta 2015), Mexico (Alvarado-Esquivel et al. 2017), and Morocco (Ait Hamou et al. 2021; Laboudi et al. 2020), Pakistan remains deficient in such data, especially in highly populated areas such as Lahore, Punjab. This study examines how birds contribute to the spread of toxoplasmosis and assesses community knowledge, attitudes, and practices (KAPs) in Lahore, Pakistan's second-largest city. Despite its public health importance, no national policies exist for controlling toxoplasmosis in Lahore or Pakistan.

Materials and Methods

Description of the study area

Lahore district, a third-level administrative unit in Punjab Province of Pakistan is the study area for this research. It comprises five tehsils (administrative sub-divisions of a district): Lahore City, Shalimar, Model Town, Raiwind, and Lahore Cantonment (Fig. 1). Covering 1772 km², Lahore has over eleven million residents, with 82.4% urban and 17.5% rural population. It represents 5.7% of Pakistan's population and 0.2% of its land area. With a semi-arid climate and distinct seasons—summer, winter, autumn, and spring—June is the hottest month (average temperature), while January is

the coldest (average temperature). In recent years, dense fog and smog have become more prevalent, especially in colder months (Hasan et al., 2022).

Figure 1. Map of the study area showing all surveyed tehsil (i.e. Lahore Cantonment; Lahore City; Model Town; Raiwind; and Shalimar) marked with dots of varying colors, enclosed within the boundary representing Lahore district.

Study design and setting

This cross-sectional study was conducted from January 25, 2023, to June 10, 2023, after approval from the Institutional Review Committee for Biomedical Research of the University of Veterinary and Animal Sciences, Lahore, Pakistan (Approval No. 227/IRC/BMR; Dated 19/01/2023). A total of 200 respondents aged 18 and above were selected using a combination of simple and systematic random sampling from five tehsils in Lahore district, where every fifth person was approached at key locations such as educational institutions, hospitals, markets, community centers, and public gathering spots following Elfil and Negida (2017). To ensure a representative sample, surveys were conducted at different times of the day and on different days of the week following Mindell et al. (2011). Participants from diverse backgrounds, including farmers, teachers, students, housewives, daily laborers, animal health, and medical professionals, were included following Yan et al. (2018). 20% of respondents (n=40) were randomly selected from different locations in five different tehsils of district

Lahore (Fig. 1). Participants were informed of their right to withdraw, anonymity, and the sole scientific purpose of the collected data (Senosy, 2020; Mahfouz et al., 2019; Desta, 2015).

Questionnaire designing, validation, and data collection

A comprehensive structured, close-ended questionnaire —adapted from Maqsood et al. (2021) — with 59 questions across five sections, assessing the community's perception and knowledge about toxoplasmosis and its role in bird transmission in English and Urdu, was designed. Face-to-face interviews were conducted after recording verbal informed consent, with no incentives given and no third-party witnesses involved, following Alghafari (2025). For validation, the KAPs questionnaire was reviewed by authors and academic experts, then piloted with 10 respondents to ensure clarity and effectiveness; pilot data were excluded from the final results following Alghafari (2025). Two trained bilingual enumerators familiar with the study and the study area conducted the surveys. The overall response rate was 95.2%.

Statistical analysis

All the data collected were entered into the Microsoft Excel 2016 spreadsheet before statistical analysis. Data were analyzed by using SPSS version 21 (IBM Armonk, New York, USA) to produce summary statistics. The outcomes were presented in percentages, frequencies, and charts. To assess statistically significant differences ($p\text{-value} \leq 0.05$) among various answers to each question or variable, the Chi-square test was conducted (Ziblim et al., 2021).

Results

Socio-demographic characteristics of study respondents

The study encompassed 200 participants, representing a diverse range of demographic characteristics, including gender, age, educational attainment, marital status, religious affiliation, and occupation (Fig. 2). There was a slightly higher proportion of males. Most participants were in the younger to middle-aged (29-38 years) and had attained education at the college or university level. A majority were married and identified as Muslim. Occupations ranged broadly, with students, teachers, and health professionals comprising a significant portion of the sample.

Figure 2. Socio-demographic characteristics of the study participants (n=200), including gender, age group, education level, marital status, religion, and current occupation. The visual summary highlights the diversity in background and professional roles across the surveyed population.

Community perspectives on birds and disease transmission

Out of 200 respondents, the majority (n=111; 55.5%) reported that birds can transmit diseases through pathogens they carry or behaviors that promote disease spread. Conversely, (n=72; 36%) stated that birds do not cause diseases, and (n=17; 8.5%) had no knowledge about this topic. Most respondents (n=95; 47.5%) believed that birds do not contribute to environmental maintenance. Interestingly, a higher percentage of respondents (n=95; 47.5%) reported that birds do not contaminate food and water sources. Regarding the potential impact of bird-borne diseases on humans, 42.5% (n=85) stated that these diseases can be fatal, while 50% (n=100) believed they cannot occur. Furthermore, 53% (n=106) of the survey participants admitted to being unaware of any signs or symptoms that birds display during illness. However, 47% (n=94) were aware of these signs and symptoms. Additionally, 52% (n=104) of the respondents acknowledged that birds (acting as vectors) can transmit diseases to humans. Notably, a significant number of respondents (n=126; 63%) expressed a lack of understanding regarding how parasitic diseases are transmitted from birds to animals and humans. Only, 37% (n=74) reported being aware of this process (Fig. 3).

Figure 3. Heatmap illustrating participants' knowledge regarding birds and disease transmission. Responses are categorized as "Yes," "No," and "Don't Know" with color intensity reflecting the percentage of respondents for each option. Chi-square (χ^2) test values are provided for each question to indicate statistical significance of response variation ($P < 0.001$).

Community awareness and misconceptions about toxoplasmosis

Among the respondents, a substantial portion (57%, n=114) were unaware of the existence of protozoan parasitic diseases and 56% (n=112) were ignorant about the symptoms associated with these

diseases. The majority of the study participants (n=84; 42%), believed *T. gondii* is a parasite, 28% (n=56) believed it to be a virus, 13.5% (n=27) thought it was a bacterium, 3% (n=6) thought it was an insect, and 13.5% (n=27) were unsure about its classification. Most participants (n=91; 45.5%) had heard or read about toxoplasmosis, while (n=88; 44%) were unaware of its existence, and (n=21; 10.5%) were uncertain. The majority of respondents (n=117; 58.5%) believed that wild birds are immune to toxoplasmosis.

A significant number (n=116; 58%) also claimed that toxoplasmosis cannot cause stillbirth or miscarriage. Furthermore, (n=114; 57%) reported that it is not possible for a mother to transmit toxoplasmosis to the fetus. Additionally, (n=90; 45%) of the study participants asserted that toxoplasmosis is not zoonotic (Fig. 4). The primary source of information about toxoplasmosis for the majority of the respondents (n=59; 29.5%) was relatives and friends.

Figure 4. Heatmap illustrating participants' knowledge regarding protozoan diseases and toxoplasmosis. Responses are categorized as "Yes," "No," "Don't Know," and "Not Sure," with color intensity reflecting the percentage of respondents for each option. Chi-square (χ^2) test values are provided for each question to indicate statistical significance of response variation (P < 0.001).

Most respondents (n=97%; 48.5%) identified animals as the hosts of toxoplasmosis. Among the respondents, (n=69; 34.5%) specifically mentioned cats and dogs as the vectors of this protozoan parasitic disease (Fig. 5).

Figure 5. Infographic showing the percentage of respondents identifying various animals as potential hosts or vectors of toxoplasmosis. Responses are categorized by type (host or vector) and associated frequency (%).

Most respondents (n=110; 55%) also claimed that birds do not act as carriers of toxoplasmosis. Approximately 49% (n=98) of the respondents reported that *T. gondii* is not shed in the feces of infected birds. Among the participants, 47.5% (n=95) were aware that *T. gondii* is present in raw or undercooked meat. Most respondents (n=101; 50.5%) reported that *T. gondii* is not present in unpasteurized milk. Out of 200 respondents, 128 (64%) had never heard or read about the definitive and intermediate hosts of toxoplasmosis. The chi-square test revealed that a significant number (n=88; 44%) of respondents reported that toxoplasmosis is associated with symptoms. Toxoplasmosis is associated with symptoms such as confusion, loss of coordination, muscle aches, blurred vision, fever, and swollen lymph nodes, among others (Fig. 6).

Figure 6. Heatmap illustrating participants' knowledge regarding birds and toxoplasmosis. The questions assess awareness of birds as potential carriers, transmission through feces, presence of *Toxoplasma gondii* in food sources, and associated symptoms. Responses are categorized as "Yes," "No," "Don't Know," and "Not Sure," with color intensity reflecting the percentage of respondents for each option. Chi-square (χ^2) test values are provided for each question to indicate statistical significance of response variation ($P < 0.001$).

Epidemiology and risk factors of toxoplasmosis

A significant portion of respondents (55%) were unaware that *T. gondii* can cause toxoplasmosis and 66% (n=132) lacked knowledge about the definitive host. However, 57.5% (n=115) of respondents believed that individuals cannot acquire toxoplasmosis through direct contact with cat or bird feces, while 47.5% (n=95) thought it can be transmitted by consuming raw or undercooked meat. Also, 45% (n=90) believed raw milk can cause toxoplasmosis, while 43% (n=86) disagreed. 43% (n=86) also reported that touching garden soil or sand can cause toxoplasmosis. Lastly, 49% (n=98) believed untreated water can cause toxoplasmosis, and 46% (n=92) reported consuming raw vegetables can cause it (Fig. 7).

Figure 7. Heatmap illustrating community knowledge of the epidemiology and risk factors of toxoplasmosis. Each question is categorized by responses "Yes," "No," and "Don't Know". Color intensity is representing the percentage of respondents. Chi-square (χ^2) values indicate statistically significant variation across responses ($P < 0.001$).

Control and treatment of toxoplasmosis

Among the respondents, 44% (n=88) believed that toxoplasmosis can be prevented, treated, and controlled, while 50% (n=100) considered awareness rising among at-risk populations as the most effective control strategy. A majority (59%; n=118) were unaware of medicines used against toxoplasmosis. Notably, 61.5% (n=123) reported that no human or animal vaccine exists. Regarding vaccine

perceptions, 43.5% (n=87) viewed vaccines as ineffective, 41.5% (n=83) supported their use, and 15% (n=30) expressed uncertainty (Fig. 8).

Figure 8. Heatmap illustrating community knowledge regarding the control and treatment of toxoplasmosis. Responses are categorized as "Yes," "No," and "Don't Know," with color intensity corresponding to the percentage of respondents. Chi-square (χ^2) test values are provided for each question to indicate statistical significance of response variation ($P < 0.001$).

Attitudes and perceptions toward toxoplasmosis

Nearly half of the respondents (47%; n=94) perceived toxoplasmosis as both an animal and human disease, while 39.5% (n=79) considered it a serious animal disease, and only 13.5% (n=27) viewed it as a serious human disease ($\chi^2 = 37.1$, $p < 0.001$). A majority (59%; n=118) regarded the disease as dangerous ($\chi^2 = 59.8$, $p < 0.001$). However, only 16% (n=32) had ever been tested for toxoplasmosis ($\chi^2 = 138.7$, $p < 0.001$). Regarding its impact, 45% (n=90) believed toxoplasmosis is harmful to humans ($\chi^2 = 42.9$, $p < 0.001$), and 44% (n=88) considered it harmful to livestock ($\chi^2 = 44.9$, $p < 0.001$). Most respondents (58.5%; n=117) reported not knowing anyone who had died from a bird transmitted infection ($\chi^2 = 68.4$, $p < 0.001$), and 50.5% (n=101) believed their families could not contract diseases from birds ($\chi^2 = 94.2$, $p < 0.001$). When asked about responses to infected birds, 52.5% (n=105) stated they did not take immediate action ($\chi^2 = 0.5$, $p = 0.5$). Similarly, 52.5% (n=105) claimed to have no direct contact with birds ($\chi^2 = 0.5$, $p = 0.5$). Nearly half (48%; n=96) disagreed with the belief that birds bring good luck ($\chi^2 = 46.4$, $p < 0.001$), a cultural notion present in many societies. In terms of dead bird disposal, 45.5% (n=91) discarded them in open areas, 32% (n=64) buried them, and 22.5% (n=45) used plastic bags ($\chi^2 = 16.0$, $p < 0.001$). Interestingly, 68% (n=136) did not agree that birds that died from disease should be buried with lime or disinfectant ($\chi^2 = 25.9$, $p < 0.001$). Knowledge about the impact of toxoplasmosis on animal production was limited, with 41.5% (n=83) admitting

they did not know ($\chi^2 = 7.6$, $p = 0.02$). In terms of preventive behavior, 57.5% (n=115) did not use protective clothing when handling animals ($\chi^2 = 4.5$, $p = 0.03$). Encouragingly, 59% (n=118) expressed willingness to support initiatives to control toxoplasmosis ($\chi^2 = 6.4$, $p = 0.01$).

Practices toward toxoplasmosis

Most respondents reported preventive practices relevant to toxoplasmosis transmission. Specifically, 58% (n=116) stored food in covered containers ($\chi^2 = 5.12$, $p = 0.02$), 70% (n=140) washed hands after handling raw meat ($\chi^2 = 32.0$, $p < 0.007$), and 76.5% (n=153) washed hands after handling sand or dirt ($\chi^2 = 56.2$, $p < 0.007$). Additionally, 68.5% (n=137) washed raw vegetables before consumption ($\chi^2 = 27.4$, $p < 0.007$), 64% (n=128) avoided unfiltered water ($\chi^2 = 15.7$, $p < 0.007$), and 61.5% (n=123) avoided ingesting raw milk ($\chi^2 = 10.6$, $p < 0.007$). Slightly over half (54%; n=108) of the participants reported separating sick animals from healthy ones, although this was not statistically significant ($\chi^2 = 1.2$, $p = 0.3$).

Discussion

Assessing the community's knowledge, attitudes, and practices (KAPs) is important for managing parasitic diseases. This study explored these aspects in the Lahore district, Punjab, Pakistan. Of the 200 respondents, 106 (53%) were unaware of any signs and symptoms that birds exhibit when they are sick. In contrast, Ayim-Akonor et al. (2020) found that 86.8% of respondents could recognize common clinical signs and symptoms shown by sick birds, although 22% could not identify the specific disease. The lower level of awareness in our study may be attributed to our respondents being from a broader community (students, teachers, housewives, etc.), who had limited direct interaction with birds, whereas Ayim-Akonor et al. (2020) specifically surveyed poultry farmers, who are more likely to observe such symptoms regularly. However, in our study, 52% were aware of the capability of birds (as vectors) to transmit diseases to humans. Similar findings were obtained in a study conducted in Ghana by Ziblim et al. (2021). Despite differences in respondents' background (i.e., livestock farmers in Ghana's study vs a mixed community in our study; Fig. 2) in both studies, this similarity in results here might be due to the impact of informal knowledge transmission, as many respondents in our study reported receiving information from relatives and friends rather than formal education. Furthermore, less than half of the respondents (37%) were aware of the transmission mechanisms of parasitic diseases from birds to animals and humans, whereas 63% were not informed about these transmission pathways. While informal knowledge transmission, such as information shared by relatives and friends, may contribute to basic awareness regarding birds as potential disease vectors, it often lacks the depth and reliability required to elucidate complex processes like the transmission

routes of parasitic diseases from birds to humans and animals. This discrepancy might explain why the majority of our participants were unaware of this transmission process. Similar results were obtained in a study conducted in Ghana by Ziblim et al. (2021), where less than half (45%) of the participants understood how diseases are transferred from animals to humans. Despite differing professional backgrounds, the outcomes are comparable, potentially due to both study populations having limited access to formal education on zoonotic diseases and relying more on informal sources of knowledge rather than formal veterinary or public health training.

Regarding the general knowledge of the community about toxoplasmosis, 42% of respondents identified *T. gondii* as a parasite. This finding is consistent with a study conducted in Rawalpindi and Islamabad, Pakistan by Maqsood et al. (2021), where 55.3% of participants shared this view. Conversely, another study by Mohammed and Kamel (2017) revealed that a majority (52.5%) perceived *T. gondii* as a virus, while 26.5% recognized it as a parasite. These discrepancies may result from differences in educational backgrounds, the presence or absence of targeted public health campaigns on toxoplasmosis, and varying awareness levels among respondents across different study locations. However, in our study 45.5% were aware of toxoplasmosis, which corresponds to the study by Maqsood et al. (2021), in which 60% of participants knew about this disease. In contrast, in Casablanca, Morocco, most pregnant women had not heard or read about toxoplasmosis, with only 41.3% aware of the disease (Ait Hamou & Laboudi, 2021). Similarly, in Ethiopia, 85.9% of the respondents had neither heard nor read about toxoplasmosis (Desta, 2015). Furthermore, a study from Gaza showed that more than 61% of participants were unaware of this disease (Dardona et al., 2023). These variations in knowledge can be attributed to differing cultural and economic backgrounds, inadequate efforts by authorities to raise awareness and knowledge of toxoplasmosis, as well as the prevention and control measures through relevant activities or educational stages, and the different target populations in various studies.

The majority (45%) of study respondents believed that toxoplasmosis is not a zoonotic disease. Similar results were observed in Ethiopia (66.2%) by Desta (2015) and Bangladesh (62.5%) by Uddin et al. (2023). However, according to Maqsood et al. (2021), 58% of participants from Islamabad and Rawalpindi recognized it as zoonotic. This difference might be due to academic orientation of the respondents in the study by Maqsood et al. (2021), where 86% were university students, mostly from biosciences and health-related fields covering zoonosis and One Health. In addition to holding higher degrees (45% Bachelor's, 29.3% Master's, 16.8% PhD, 9% Post-doc), the respondents in that study showed strong awareness of zoonotic concepts (60.3% knew "zoonosis", 61.5% were familiar with

"One Health"). This contrasts with our study population, which participants were from mixed educational and occupational backgrounds (Fig. 2), with majority without any exposure to disease ecology or host-pathogen interaction concepts.

However, regarding birds' role in transmission, 55% stated that birds are not carriers of toxoplasmosis. This aligns with findings of Uddin et al. (2023) from Bangladesh, where 88.6% denied birds' role in transmission, and 90.2% stated chickens are not carriers. This suggests a general lack of awareness regarding birds as disease vectors. In our study, 49% of respondents did not believe *T. gondii* is shed in bird feces. In Ethiopia, 57.1% of cat owners were unsure about fecal shedding in cats (Desta 2015), while 75.3% in Pakistan correctly recognized shedding of *T. gondii* in cat feces (Maqsood et al., 2021). This difference possibly reflects differences in educational exposure across the study populations in Maqsood's study as discussed earlier. Participants in both this study and Desta (2015) lacked formal education in veterinary or public health. Despite being cat owners, Desta's participants were unsure about fecal shedding, indicating that owning animals alone does not ensure disease-specific knowledge without targeted education. Furthermore, public health messaging on this disease tends to focus more on cats as compared to birds, which may be attributed to the lower recognition of bird-related transmission routes observed in our study.

About 47.5% of our participants acknowledged *T. gondii*'s presence in undercooked meat, consistent with Maqsood et al. (2021). However, findings contradict those from Ethiopia, where 66% were unsure (Desta, 2015). Regarding milk, 50.5% of respondents in our study denied *T. gondii*'s presence in unpasteurized milk, which contrasts with Maqsood et al. (2021), where 67.8% affirmed its presence. The lack of knowledge about transmission routes remains a barrier to prevention and highlights the need for continuous health education (Tung et al., 2008). Furthermore, 66% were unaware of its definitive host. In Morocco, 89.4% did not know *T. gondii* causes toxoplasmosis (Ait Hamou and Laboudi 2021), while health professionals in Rabat showed much higher knowledge (Laboudi et al., 2020). Similarly, in Mexico, 89.6% correctly identified the parasite and 83.8% recognized cats as definitive hosts (Alvarado-Esquivel et al., 2017). These differences may be due to the absence of targeted screening and awareness programs in Pakistan.

Respondents in our study showed moderate awareness of transmission routes: 47.5% recognized undercooked meat, 43% soil, 49% untreated water, and 46% raw vegetables. These findings align with the results presented in Maqsood et al. (2021), while contradicting Desta (2015), whose study conducted in Ethiopia revealed that 69.8% of respondents did not perceive undercooked meat as a risk factor. In our study, 45% did not think raw milk could transmit the disease, which is consistent with Ethiopian findings, where 89.7% of pregnant women (a high-risk group) consumed raw milk and

believed that it does not transmit toxoplasmosis (Desta, 2015). However, multiple studies have reported a positive association between consumption of raw milk and human infection with toxoplasmosis (Boughattas, 2015; Jones et al., 2009). Our finding reflects a common misunderstanding rooted in traditional consumption habits, where raw milk is viewed as natural and healthful (Claeys et al., 2013). The low recognition of raw milk as a risk factor in current study is likely due to lack of targeted education addressing this lesser-known pathway of *T. gondii* infection. One way to approach this issue would be to develop educational outreach programs for the general public, that focuses on issues related to the consumption of raw milk.

Only 44% of respondents believed toxoplasmosis could be prevented or treated. This aligns with findings from Southern Ethiopia (Fesseha & Abebe, 2020). In addition, most respondents (61.5%) were unaware of vaccine availability, similar to reports from Morocco (Laboudi et al., 2020). While no human vaccine exists, this highlights the need for promoting preventive measures.

Nearly half (47%) of participants perceived toxoplasmosis as a serious animal and human disease, with 59% considering it dangerous. This aligns with Maqsood et al. (2021), where 65.8% and 80% of respondents expressed similar views. However, 52.5% of our participants did not take immediate rescue action for infected birds. These outcomes are in contrast with previous study in Jinka town, Ethiopia, where the majority (17.9%) of the high school students reported taking immediate action, such as reporting and isolating infected animals (Fesseha & Abebe, 2020). This discrepancy might be due to the Ethiopian respondents' regular exposure to domestic animals and school-based animal health education, whereas many participants of our study had limited direct contact with birds and lacked formal training in basic biosecurity procedures. In this study, 68% did not know that infected birds should be buried with lime or disinfectant. In contrast, 88.7% of respondents in Greece supported this practice (Moutos et al., 2022). This difference is possibly due to contrasting study populations. The study by Moutos et al. (2022) involved livestock farmers, who often engage in animal care practices and may receive routine guidance on carcass disposal. On the other hand, our study's participants were drawn from general public, where such knowledge is less emphasized, and safe disposal of sick or dead birds might not be considered a priority.

About 41.5% of the respondents did not know that toxoplasmosis affects the production of animals. In contrast, Maqsood et al. (2021) reported that 70.3% of participants were aware of its impact on livestock. In the current study, 57.5% of the respondents did not use protective clothing while handling animals. In contrast, a previous study reported that the majority of the participants (64.5%) used personal protective equipment for handling cats (Maqsood et al., 2021). Our outcomes are also in contrast with the findings of Moutos et al. (2022), where more than half of the respondents (94.1%) reported that they wear protective clothing while working on farm. Most of the participants (59%) in

our study expressed support for initiatives aimed at controlling this protozoan parasitic disease. This figure is lower compared to the 83% reported by Maqsood et al. (2021). These variations likely stem from differences in educational backgrounds and occupations, as previously discussed. An additional significant factor contributing to these outcome disparities may be the absence of survey programs and research initiatives designed to determine the prevalence, risk factors, distribution, and public health significance of toxoplasmosis in the study region.

Our study revealed that 58% of respondents stored their food in covered containers which aligns with findings of a previous study (Maqsood et al. 2021), where 86.5% reported the same. Additionally, 70% and 76.5% of our respondents washed their hands after handling raw meat and sand or dirt, respectively. These outcomes are consistent with Desta (2015), who reported that 62.2% washed their hands after handling raw meat, and 77.6% washed their hands after handling sand and dirt or after gardening. Among Muslims, eating directly with hands is considered *Sunnah* (the practices and teachings of the Prophet Muhammad (PBUH)). It is also regarded as part of cultural etiquette in certain regions of Pakistan. However, if hands are not thoroughly washed, they could be a source of infection, especially after contact with cat feces or soil as it poses a risk of unintended ingestion of oocysts (Ngu et al., 2011). These practices may not stem solely from disease-specific knowledge, but might also be influenced by religious teachings that emphasize handwashing through ablution (*wudu*) before eating and daily prayers, reinforcing habitual cleanliness. Although religious or cultural influences may vary across different populations, these practices can contribute to general hygiene awareness. Furthermore, 68.5% washed vegetables, 64% avoided unfiltered water, and 61% avoided raw milk. These findings are comparable to studies in Indonesia and Morocco (Nurseha et al., 2023; Ait Hamou & Laboudi, 2021). In contrast, studies in Ethiopia showed low avoidance rates (Desta, 2015). This variation of these outcomes could be attributed to the difference in the cultural, occupation and educational background of the participants. Notably, 54% in our study separated sick animals from healthy ones, similar to Maqsood *et al.* (2021), where 78.3% did so, suggesting some practical awareness despite limited formal knowledge.

Conclusion

This study provides important baseline insights into the community's KAPs regarding toxoplasmosis and the role of birds in its transmission in Lahore, Pakistan's second-largest metropolitan city. The findings indicate limited to moderate awareness among respondents, with significant gaps in understanding the zoonotic nature of the disease, its transmission routes, and the epidemiological role of birds. Given the absence of national policies for toxoplasmosis prevention in Pakistan, targeted educational initiatives are urgently needed. Public health campaigns should use the One Health approach

to educate urban and rural populations on symptoms, prevention, and control. Regular screening in humans and animals could further help identify local epidemiological patterns and inform future interventions. These findings offer a valuable foundation for designing surveillance and control programs for toxoplasmosis and other parasitic zoonoses in Lahore and similar settings globally.

Limitations

The small sample size and non-random sampling limit the generalizability of findings. The cross-sectional design restricts analysis of temporal trends. Language translation from English to Urdu may have introduced interpretational bias, and cultural dynamics, such as male interviewers engaging female respondents, could have influenced responses. Socioeconomic differences between interviewers and participants may also have affected disclosure. Future studies should use representative sampling, longitudinal designs, gender-matched interviewers, and culturally sensitive methods to enhance validity.

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